

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DIALLO****FIRST NAME: GAELLE****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 24 %

The author used the following software: MSWord 2021 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Can writer use both the US and UK English in the same paper?

The writer must use only one version of English throughout the paper but use the original English version when citing a quotation.¹

Yes, the writer can use both at the same time.

No, the writer can only choose one.

Only when it can be justified.

2. What is the purpose of a qualitative proposal?

It is chosen when the researcher is not presenting data.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 86.

- To present a clear argument that explains and justifies the logic of the study.**²
 - It is used to support the methodology.
 - It is used to discuss literature reviews.
3. What are the necessary elements to build a strong proposal?
- The argument presented.
 - The research question and data collected.
 - A clear problem statement, a purpose statement, a research question, a review of the relevant literature research, data collection and data analysis methods.**³
 - No elements are necessary if the researcher presents valid data to support the hypothesis.
4. How does a scholar choose a research approach?
- Based on the researcher beliefs.
 - A brief overview of the argument.
 - Based only on the research.
 - A qualitative proposal presents a clear argument that explains and justifies the logic of the study.**⁴
5. What is the purpose of a qualitative proposal?
- The qualitative research approach is chosen based on the research problem.**⁵
 - To discuss literature review.

² Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2018), 202.

³ Ibid., 202.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Ibid., 135.

- To discuss human factors in the research.
 - It is used when quantitative research is not appropriate.
6. What are the best sources of information?
- Popular magazines.
 - Commentary and opinion journals.
 - Most recent primary and secondary sources.**⁶
 - Any publications holding the subject of the dissertation.
7. What type of literature review does a scholar need to support their research?
- Any published article.
 - A Peer-review literature including journals and academic papers.**⁷
 - Any article with an abstract.
 - Articles found on selected databases discussing the topic of research.
8. Does the methodology always have to include genres or traditions?
- The scholar must choose one or more genres to provide specific direction regarding the research design and research methods.**⁸
 - No, the scholar can omit the genres or tradition.
 - It depends on the topic of research.
 - It depends on the methodology of data collection.
9. What is the role of a qualitative researcher?
- To provide their findings based on their beliefs.

⁶ Ibid., 77.

⁷ Ibid., 353.

⁸ Ibid., 157.

- To provide data and let the reader interpret them.
- The researcher endeavors to explain the meaning of the findings from the perspective of the research participants.⁹**
- To describe findings and let the reader interpret them.

10. When is the abstract of a dissertation written?

- The abstract is written first.
- The abstract is written alongside the dissertation.
- Anytime during the process of data collection.
- The abstract is written after the dissertation is completed.¹⁰**

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie F. Volpe: *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2018.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

⁹ Ibid., 151.

¹⁰ Ibid., 68.